

Designing a Model for Description of Theses and Dissertations Information on a Large Scale

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Alidousti, S., M. Khosrowjerdi, P. Shahriari, F. Shirani, and H. Beyrami

Abstract:

Theses and dissertations as the main products of the process of research at graduate and post-graduate levels are among the most important scientific documents of any country. By themselves, in combination, or in comparison with data from other sources of information, the set of data from such documents can provide a new source of information which is highly valuable from scientific and managerial points of view.

However, a review of the related literature indicates that there is no uniform model which can incorporate all the various dimensions of these documents. The present article reports on the results of a study carried out to construct a comprehensive.

Model to describe and analyze the information on theses and dissertations .To this end, the research problem is initially defined, followed by a literature review. The article continues with a description of the research method which involves the Delphi Method and a feasibility test. The study resulted in the identification of a total of 184 describable and analyzable items of information on theses and dissertations and their relevant information. The information items were classified into three categories including information on theses and dissertations, information related to them, and mixed information, all of which are discussed in terms of 12 different aspects.